

Spam Classification In Indonesian-Language Emails Using FastText and Bernoulli Naïve Bayes

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Indonesia ranks sixth globally in terms of the number of spam senders. Numerous studies have been conducted on spam detection and filtering, with Bayesian algorithms being among the most commonly used approaches. This study aims to classify Indonesian-language email messages into spam and non-spam categories. A secondary dataset consisting of 2.604 messages was used, comprising 1.362 spam messages and 1.242 non-spam messages. Word representation was performed using FastText with an n-gram approach to capture sub-word level information, while classification was carried out using the Bernoulli Naïve Bayes algorithm based on binary values. The experiments compared the performance of the Bernoulli Naïve Bayes algorithm with and without the use of FastText. Evaluation was conducted using accuracy, confusion matrix, and classification report metrics, with a 70:30 data split. The result showed that both models, with and without FastText demonstrated more balanced performance across classes and higher recall in detecting spam. In contrast, the model without FastText achieved perfect precision and recall for spam but showed decreased performance for non-spam. Therefore, the use of FastText contributes to improving the sensitivity and balance of spam email classification in the Indonesian language.

1. Introduction

Email spam refers to unsolicited bulk messages, often containing advertisements, fraud attempts, or harmful content such as malicious links or attachments. Since the early 1990s, spam has become a growing challenge in digital communication. According to AV-Test statistic, Indonesia ranks sixth globally in terms of the number of spam senders [1].

Research in spam classification has progressed significantly, with Bayesian algorithms being among the most commonly used approaches due to their simplicity and computational efficiency [2]. Among its variants, Bernoulli Naïve Bayes is considered effective for binary text classification tasks particularly when dealing with limited datasets [3].

To improve classification accuracy, word representation using word embedding is essential [4]. One of the notable models in this area is FastText, which can handle out-of-vocabulary words by utilizing sub-word information through character n-grams [5]. FastText has shown to be effective in modeling morphologically rich languages such as Indonesian [6][7].

This study aims to implement FastText as the word representation model and Bernoulli Naïve Bayes as the classification algorithm to detect spam in Indonesian-language emails. The combination of these methods is expected to deliver accurate and efficient spam classification performance.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Email Spam

Email spam refers to unsolicited electronic messages sent in bulk, often containing advertisements, phishing attempts, malware, or other malicious content. Spam messages can disrupt users, overload networks, and increase cybersecurity risks [8]. According to Cormack [9], despite the various spam filtering techniques developed, key challenges remain in maintaining the accuracy and efficiency of spam detection systems. Regularly updated training data is critical due to the evolving tactics used by spammers.

2.2 Text Classification and Preprocessing

Text classification is the process of assigning predefined labels to textual data based on certain features [10]. To improve performance, text data typically undergoes preprocessing steps such as:

- Cleaning, removing special characters, numbers, and irrelevant symbols.
- Case Folding, converting all text to lowercase to avoid redundancy.
- Tokenizing, Splitting text into individual words or tokens.
- Stopword Removal, eliminating common words that provide little semantic value (e.g., “dan”, “di”, “ke”).
- Stemming, reducing words to their root form to minimize word variations.

These steps are crucial for reducing data complexity and enhancing feature quality before classification.

2.3 FastText

FastText, developed by Facebook AI Research, is a word embedding and text classification model that extends Word2Vec by incorporating sub-word (n-gram) information. This allows the model to generalize better, especially when dealing with morphologically rich languages or rare words [6].

$$v_w = \frac{1}{|G_w|} \sum_{g \in G_w} z_g \quad (1)$$

Where:

- v_w is the final representation vector for the word w .
- G_w is the set of n-gram characters from the word w .
- $|G_w|$ is the total number of n-grams in G_w .
- z_g is the vector representation of the n-gram character g (generated by FastText during training).

Words are represented as the sum or average of their character n-gram vectors, enabling the model to generate meaningful embedding for out-of-vocabulary terms. FastText has proven effective in various NLP tasks, including those involving the Indonesian language [11][7].

2.4 Bernoulli Naïve Bayes

Bernoulli Naïve Bayes is a probabilistic classifier derived from Bayes' theorem. It models binary features, representing the presence or absence of words in a document. The probability of a document belonging to a specific class is calculated based on these binary features [12]. This model is particularly suitable for text classification tasks with limited data, and prior studies have demonstrated its superior performance compared to other Naïve Bayes variants.

$$P(x_i | C_k) = \prod_{i=1}^n (p_{k_i}^{x_i} (1 - p_{k_i})^{(1-x_i)}) \quad (2)$$

Where:

- p_{k_i} is the probability that feature x_i appears in class C_k .
- x_i is a binary value (0 or 1) that indicates the presence or absence of that feature in the document.

3. Methodology

This study uses a secondary dataset obtained from Kaggle, titled Indonesian Email Spam Dataset. The dataset contains 2.604 email messages, consisting of 1362 spam messages and 1242 non-spam messages. Each record includes the full email content and its label (spam or non-spam). This study has the following framework.

Fig. 1. Framework Plan

a) Data Preprocessing

Preprocessing is essential for converting unstructured text into a structured format suitable for machine learning. The following steps were applied:

- **Cleaning**, removing special characters, punctuation, numbers, and irrelevant symbols.
- **Cleaning**, converting all characters to lowercase.
- **Tokenizing**, splitting text into individual tokens or words.
- **Stopword Removal**, removing common words with little semantic value (e.g., “dan”, “di”, “ke”).
- **Stemming**, reducing words to their root form to minimize word variations.

b) Word Representation using FastText

After preprocessing, the clean text was converted into vector representations using the FastText unsupervised model. FastText maps each word into a dense vector space based on character-level n-grams, allowing the model to handle out-of-vocabulary words effectively.

c) Classification using Bernoulli Naïve Bayes

After preprocessing the data and representing it with FastText, the classification process used the Bernoulli Naïve Bayes algorithm, with the following steps:

- **Binarization**, FastText vectors were binarized (converted into 0 and 1) to suit Bernoulli Naïve Bayes input format.
- **Training**, the model was trained on the training set.
- **Classification**, the trained model predicted label for the test set.

4. Result and Discussion

This section presents the experimental results of the proposed spam email classification using FastText word representation and Bernoulli Naïve Bayes classifier. The evaluation was conducted in three scenarios to assess the impact of train-test data split ratio, model performance evaluation, and comparative analysis between Bernoulli Naïve Bayes with and without FastText representation.

4.1 Scenario I – Impact of Train-Test Split Ratio

The first scenario evaluates the effect of different train-test split ratios (70:30, 80:20, and 90:10) on the classification performance. Table 1 shows the accuracy, precision, recall, and f1-score obtained for each split ratio.

Table 1. Performance Comparison of Different Train-Test Splits

Split Ratio	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-Score
70:30	0.93	0.90	0.96	0.92

80:20	0.92	0.90	0.96	0.92
90:10	0.93	0.92	0.96	0.93

Based on Table 1, the 70:30 split ratio provided the most balanced and consistent performance, making it the preferred configuration for subsequent experiments.

4.2 Scenario II – Evaluation of FastText + Bernoulli Naïve Bayes

In the second scenario, the model was trained with a 70:30 split ratio, and evaluated using accuracy, precision, recall and f1-score for both spam and non-spam classes.

Table 2. Classification Performance of FastText + Bernoulli Naïve Bayes

Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Accuracy
Spam	0.93	0.98	0.96	0.95
Non-Spam	0.98	0.92	0.95	0.95

The confusion matrix in Table 3 shows high true positive (TP) and true negative (TN) counts, indicating that the model accurately classifies both spam and non-spam emails.

Table 3. Confusion Matrix of FastText + Bernoulli Naïve Bayes

Actual	Predicted	
	Spam	Non-spam
Spam	401	8
Non-spam	28	345

Furthermore, the ROC curve (Fig. 2) demonstrates an AUC value close to 1, which indicates excellent discriminative ability. The precision-recall curve (Fig. 3) also confirms stable performance even in the presence of slight class imbalance.

Fig. 2. ROC curve for FastText + Bernoulli Naïve Bayes

Fig. 3. Precision-Recall curve for FastText + Bernoulli Naïve Bayes

4.3 Scenario III – Comparative Analysis with and without FastText

The third scenario compares Bernoulli Naïve Bayes with and without FastText word representation. The result in Table 4, indicate that while Bernoulli Naïve Bayes without FastText achieved perfect recall for spam (1.00), it also produced more false positives by misclassifying non-spam emails as spam. On the other hand, the Bernoulli Naïve Bayes with FastText combination demonstrated a better balance between precision and recall across both classes, making it reliable for general spam filtering.

Table 4. Performance Comparison

Model	Class	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Accuracy
With FastText	Spam	0.93	0.98	0.96	0.95
	Non-Spam	0.98	0.92	0.95	0.95
Without FastText	Spam	0.92	1.00	0.96	0.95
	Non-Spam	1.00	0.91	0.95	0.95

4.4 Discussion

From the experiments, it can be concluded that integrating FastText representation with Bernoulli Naïve Bayes yields robust spam classification for Indonesian emails. FastText effectively captures sub-word information, enabling better handling of morphological variations and informal language. This contributes to the model's high accuracy (95%) and balanced precision-recall performance, as confirmed by ROC and Precision-Recall analysis.

The comparative results also highlight that while raw Bernoulli Naïve Bayes can excel in recall for spam, the inclusion of FastText reduces false positives and enhances overall reliability, which is crucial for real-word email filtering systems.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that the combination of FastText word embedding and Bernoulli Naïve Bayes algorithm provides a highly effective approach for classifying spam in Indonesian-language emails. Experimental results showed that the model achieved an accuracy of 95%, with balanced precision and recall for both spam and non-spam classes. The high True Positive and True Negative values in the confusion matrix, along with ROC and Precision-Recall curves close to optimal, confirm the model's string discriminatory ability and stable performance across classes.

5.1 Implications

- Practical/Managerial: The proposed approach offers a lightweight and computationally efficient solution for spam detection systems, particularly suitable for Indonesian email platforms with limited resources.
- Theoretical: This work reinforces evidence that sub-word based embeddings such as FastText are effective for morphologically rich languages and are well suited for binary classification tasks like spam filtering.

5.2 Limitations

- The dataset used was secondary and sourced from a single repository (Kaggle) potentially limiting language style and spam variety coverage.
- The FastText implementation was constrained to numpy versions below 2.0, reducing compatibility with newer environments.
- Bernoulli Naïve Bayes relies on binary features and does not directly utilize term frequency information, which may affect certain classification contexts.

5.3 Suggestion for Future Research

- Utilize larger and more diverse datasets, including real-world and recent email corpora, to enhance model generalization.
- Explore alternative classification algorithms such as Logistic Regression, Random Forest, or deep learning architectures for comparative performance analysis.
- Implement hybrid feature representation combining sub-word embeddings with term-frequency-based features for potentially better results.
- Investigate cross-lingual spam detection to assess model robustness for mixed language or transliterated content.

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